

Identifying Psychological Effects of Social Media using Machine learning approach

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ABSTRACT

Purpose: Social Media have been developed as a useful tool for its users to communicate with friends and share their thoughts, pictures based on their situations and sentiments. These tools have become very popular wide over the world and each tool has billions of users. Using these tools we can analyze the data to understand their sentiments and feelings and find their problems.

Approach: Identifying the psychological effects using social media data is in an established position globally; but still there are other aspects that are to be studied. We aim to scrutinize the data collected from Twitter and Instagram to investigate the psychological effects on the users of Twitter and Instagram, we are planning to use Machine learning (ML) approach for effective results.

Outcome: By implementing the proposed approach using a set of various psychological behaviors, we can have the significant improvement in the accuracy and reduce error rate. Also, we can achieve expected results using a specific algorithm which gives the highest accuracy among ML approaches to find the psychological effects.

Conclusions: Sentimental Analysis can be carried out efficiently using ML approaches.

Keywords: Mental health of social media users, Psychological analysis of tweets, Analysis of behavior change, ML techniques

1. INTRODUCTION

The internet and communication technologies and especially the social media have empowered the people to interact with each other electronically. Users of platforms such as Twitter and Instagram are free to express their feelings, emotions and sentiments about a topic, subject or an issue online [1]. This is wonderful for users of platforms to express their feelings openly and freely to any topic online; but also, it creates opportunities for health sector people to understand the mental state of a person who reacted to a post in a particular manner. In order to get into such insight, ML approach could possibly offer some unique features that can support in inspecting the unique patterns invisible in online communication and process them to reveal the mental state among social media users. Furthermore, there is growth in the literature addressing the role of social media on the architecture of social relationships such as divorce, breakup, mental stress, smoking and drinking habits, domestic violence, sexual harassment and suicide attempts [2].

2. LITERATURE SURVEY

Our aim is to understand social media data to identify any factors that may reflect the psycholinguistic effects on Social media users. Various ML approaches are used for such purpose. This insight underlines the mental health and emotional conditions of the users, chiefly among adolescent and youth population. The challenge is to identify the users who are showing signs of succumbing to mental illness at its onset. In the proposed method, we have proposed review of unsupervised algorithms on the data, signaling behavior change for psychological analysis and identify the probability of users showing at-risk behavior [3]. By at-risk behavior, we mean users who are on the verge of acquiring some mental illness. In this study, we analyzed posts and tweets from the social media platform namely Twitter and reviewed an unsupervised model proposed in literature to classify users based on the ML techniques.

3. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The main benefactions of the paper are listed as follows:

1. Review the literature on various emotion detection techniques to detect psychological mental health effects.
2. Identify four features for our specific research problem.
3. Survey experiments on datasets of Twitter, Instagram user comments.
4. Suggest ML approaches to utilize all factors to improve accuracy. Identify Decision Tree classifier as tool for sentimental analysis on our future research.

4. MATERIALS AND METHODS

We will first focus on three factors, namely, emotion pattern, temporal pattern and the linguistic pattern as feature for the detection and processing of psychological data received on Twitter and Instagram posts. We then study supervised ML approaches to study each factor independently. The classification approaches such as ‘decision tree’, ‘k-Nearest Neighbor’, ‘Support Vector Machine’ are suitable. Following are the steps to be applied for finding the psychological effects using the posts/comments in social media.

- Data set extraction
- Feature extraction
- Measuring psychological behavior

The above steps can be sub divided as

- Psychological pattern—

Affective pattern, social pattern, cognitive pattern, perceptual pattern, biological pattern, drives, time orientations, relativity, personal issues.

- Linguistic pattern —

Number of words, sentences, articles, all types of pronouns, verbs, adverbs, prepositions, conjunctions, Negations etc.

- Other grammar—

Interrogatives, number, quantifiers, verbs, adverbs, adjectives, comparisons.

- Biological processes—

Health, body, sexual and ingestion.

- The Affective processes are anger, sadness, anxiety, positive emotion and negative emotions.
- Time orientation means present, past, future indications.
- Social processes are family, friends, and male, female.
- Perceptual processes is seeing, hearing, and feeling [4].

5. TIMELINE

Following activities will be done in order to complete the research and come to a conclusion.

- **Data set inspection**

We will work on comments posted by users in Twitter for psychological behavioural exploration and detection.

1. Collect data from the social media.
2. Preparation of data using comments posted by users in Twitter is one of the primary challenges which contain information on whether or not they could possess psychological content.
3. Performing qualitative data analysis of the captured social media content.

- **Data set preparation**

Post the collection of the raw data from users' posts, review comments from Twitter we will analyse it by using suitable software that will heart of our software engine which will do the text analysis and can process text on a word by word basis. Our dataset contains information that represents the linguistic pattern (articles, verbs, pronouns, prepositions, conjunctions, impersonal pronouns, negation etc.)

- **Feature Extraction**

Feature Extraction and demonstration amongst psychological and non-psychological effecting posts, we extract the different features by looking at the psycholinguistic measurements from different users post.

- **Measuring psychological behaviour**

Finally, with all the information and data sets we will measure the psychological effects on human mind.

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